

Experimental / Images

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API Version: 1.0.0

Organize and search the images of the construction site.

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API

1. IMAGES

1.1 GET /images/within_bounding_box

Get Images Within Bounding Box

Retrieve images captured within the given bounding box.

REQUEST

REQUEST BODY - application/json

```
{  
  Represent a query to the image database based on a bounding box.  
  interval_start* integer Time stamp when the first image was captured (inclusive, seconds since epoch in UTC)  
  interval_end*   integer Time stamp after the last image was captured (exclusive, seconds since epoch in UTC)  
  source_urls*    [string]  
  bounding_box {  
    Represent a bounding box of an image query.  
    xmin* number inclusive  
    xmax* number exclusive  
    ymin* number inclusive  
    ymax* number exclusive  
    zmin* number inclusive  
    zmax* number exclusive  
  }  
}
```

RESPONSE

STATUS CODE - 200: Successful Response

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

```
[ {  
  Array of object: Represent a retrievable image from our system.  
  timestamp* integer Timestamp when the image was taken (seconds since epoch in UTC)  
  location* {  
    Represent space coordinates where the image was taken.  
    x* number  
    y* number  
    z* number  
  }  
  angle_of_view* {  
    Specify the diagonal angle of view of an image.  
    TODO (mrustin, 2021-04-16): We need yet to specify this.  
  }  
  direction* {  
    Represent the compass direction of the camera when the image was taken.  
    TODO (mrustin, 2021-04-16): We need yet to specify this.  
  }  
  url* string  
}
```

STATUS CODE - 422: Validation Error

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

```
{
  detail [{
    Array of object:
    loc* [string]
    msg* string
    type* string
  }]
}
```

1.2 GET /images/of_elements

Get Images Of Elements

Retrieve images capturing the elements in their field-of-view.

REQUEST

REQUEST BODY - application/json

```
{
  Represent a query to the image database based on building elements.
  interval_start* integer Time stamp when the first image was captured (inclusive, seconds since epoch in UTC)
  interval_end* integer Time stamp after the last image was captured (exclusive, seconds since epoch in UTC)
  source_urls* [string]
  elements* [{
    Array of object: Specify the relevant building element for a query.
    guid* string PATTERN:^[a-zA-Z0-9_ . :- ]+$
      Generally unique identifier of the element
    revision_url* string URL to the revision of the building plan (*e.g.*, in BIM Sync)
    url* string URL to the description of the element (*e.g.*, in BIM Sync)
  }]
}
```

RESPONSE

STATUS CODE - 200: Successful Response

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

```
[{
  Array of object: Represent a retrievable image from our system.
  timestamp* integer Timestamp when the image was taken (seconds since epoch in UTC)
  location* {
    Represent space coordinates where the image was taken.
    x* number
    y* number
    z* number
  }
  angle_of_view* {
    Specify the diagonal angle of view of an image.
    TODO (mristin, 2021-04-16): We need yet to specify this.
  }
  direction* {
    Represent the compass direction of the camera when the image was taken.
    TODO (mristin, 2021-04-16): We need yet to specify this.
  }
  url* string
}]
```

STATUS CODE - 422: Validation Error

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

```
{
  detail [{
    Array of object:
    loc* [string]
    msg* string
    type* string
  }]
}
```

1.3 POST /images

Post Image

Upload an image together with its meta-data.

Return URL of the image.

REQUEST

FORM DATA PARAMETERS

NAME	TYPE	DESCRIPTION
file	string(binary)	
image	string	JSON-encoded meta data in form of Image structure.

RESPONSE

STATUS CODE - 200: Successful Response

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

undefined

STATUS CODE - 422: Validation Error

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

```
{
  detail [{
    Array of object:
    loc* [string]
    msg* string
    type* string
  }]
}
```

1.4 GET /images/{image_path}

Get Image

Check if the image exists.

REQUEST

PATH PARAMETERS

NAME	TYPE	DESCRIPTION
*image_path	string	

RESPONSE

STATUS CODE - 200: Successful Response

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

undefined

RESPONSE MODEL - image/png

STATUS CODE - 404: Image not available

STATUS CODE - 422: Validation Error

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

```
{
  detail [{
    Array of object:
      loc* [string]
      msg* string
      type* string
    }]
}
```

1.5 HEAD /images/{image_path}

Image Exists

Check if the image exists.

REQUEST

QUERY PARAMETERS

NAME	TYPE	DESCRIPTION
*path	string	

RESPONSE

STATUS CODE - 200: Image available

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

undefined

STATUS CODE - 404: Image not available

STATUS CODE - 422: Validation Error

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

```
{
  detail [{
    Array of object:
      loc* [string]
      msg* string
      type* string
    }]
}
```

} }]

2. SOURCES

2.1 GET /sources

Get Sources

List all sources of all the images available in the database.

REQUEST

No request parameters

RESPONSE

STATUS CODE - 200: Successful Response

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

[string]
